

5 Sector-detailed urban Greenhouse Gas Emission Futures derived from the ScenarioMIP-CMIP7 ensemble

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Abstract

45 **Required emission reductions for reaching the goals of the Paris Agreement have been extensively**
6 **analyzed in scenarios of integrated assessment modeling. However, the contribution of urban**
7 **areas in aggregate, globally, by region and by city type, remains underexplored. Here, we develop**
8 **a spatially explicit framework to downscale global emissions pathways to urban areas,**
9 **differentiated by region and city type. Ambitious climate change mitigation could deliver 21**
10 **GtCO₂e of greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reductions in urban areas by 2050 relative to**
11 **continuation of current policies and trends, primarily by transitioning away from fossil fuels for**
12 **electricity and heat supply, deep decarbonization of industry, and mitigation action in the**
13 **transportation and buildings sectors. Mitigation potential is concentrated in established cities as**
14 **well as in rapidly growing cities globally, reflecting their high current per-capita emission levels.**
15 **Asian regions with high urbanization levels dominate global urban emissions and reduction**
16 **potentials. The findings underscore the central role of cities in achieving global climate targets**
17 **and highlight the importance of differentiated mitigation strategies across regions and city types.**

1. Introduction

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27 60 Cities are central to global climate change mitigation because they concentrate people, economic
28 activity, infrastructure, and energy demand (Seto *et al* 2014). Urban areas account for roughly 70%
29 of global final energy use and a similar share of energy-related CO₂ emissions, making them critical
30 sites for mitigation action (Lwasa *et al* 2022). At the same time, cities offer substantial mitigation
31 opportunities across buildings, transport, energy supply (Creutzig *et al* 2016), and urban form
32 (Creutzig *et al* 2015), many of which are cost-effective and deliver significant co-benefits such as
33 65 improved air quality, health, and accessibility (Becvarik *et al* 2024, Castillo *et al* 2021, Creutzig *et al*
34 2025).

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41 70 Despite their central role, the evolution of the urban share in global emissions across sectors and city
42 types remains poorly quantified, limiting the ability to align subnational action with national and
43 global climate targets. Scenarios from integrated assessment models (IAMs) have long served as
44 primary tools for the exploration of emissions futures (Weyant 2017) providing crucial inputs for
45 climate policy making (UNFCCC 2023, IPCC 2022), financial risk assessment (NGFS 2024, Bertram *et al*
46 2021), and Earth System Modeling (O'Neill *et al* 2016, Gidden *et al* 2019, van Vuuren *et al* 2025).

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55 75 However, IAMs are limited in geographical resolution and typically represent 12–32 aggregated
56 world regions, lacking the spatial granularity required to capture subnational heterogeneity,
57 including differences between urban and rural energy use and emissions patterns. There are only
58 very few examples that use variants of IAMs to directly analyze city-level emissions. Weber *et al.*
59 (2024) and Waite *et al.* (2024) used the GCAM model to analyse climate change mitigation strategies
60 for Kuala Lumpur and Bangkok, respectively. Based on an energy systems model, Jacobson *et al.*
(2018) derived transformation pathways for US cities. Other studies used IAMs to determine urban
and rural emissions for the transport and residential sectors for selected countries (Yin *et al* 2015,
Krey *et al* 2012, Daioglou *et al* 2012). Others leverage IAM-derived scenarios to benchmark
subnational mitigation efforts against current national policy efforts or to evaluate their aggregate
global impact (Kuramochi *et al* 2020, Hsu *et al* under review). However, these approaches do not

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3 provide a comprehensive, sector-resolved assessment of the aggregate urban contribution to global
4 85 emissions across a wide range of mitigation scenarios.

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7 Addressing this gap requires downscaling global emissions pathways to the urban scale in a manner
8 that preserves sectoral dynamics and scenario consistency. Downscaling IAM scenarios is an
9 established practice (van Vuuren *et al* 2010, Grübler *et al* 2007). Gurney *et al.* (2022) combine
10 historical urban per-capita consumption-based CO₂ emissions (Moran *et al* 2018) with projections
11 90 from the Shared-Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) to derive urban emission scenarios under
12 alternative socio-economic developments and global mitigation goals, but do not resolve emissions
13 across sectors or capture sector-specific decarbonization dynamics.

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17 Here, we develop a spatially explicit downscaling framework that links global emissions pathways
18 from the ScenarioMIP–CMIP7 ensemble (van Vuuren *et al* 2025) with gridded socio-economic
19 95 projections and urban settlement patterns. This approach enables the derivation of sector-resolved
20 GHG emission pathways for urban areas, differentiated by world regions and city types. We address
21 three questions: (i) How does the urban contribution to global GHG emissions evolve across sectors
22 under different climate policy scenarios? (ii) How do mitigation potentials vary across regions and
23 city types? (iii) What role do cities play in achieving deep emission reductions consistent with the
24 goals of the Paris Agreement?
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28 Our results provide a systematic and sector-resolved perspective on the role of urban areas in global
29 mitigation pathways, offering insights to inform city-level climate strategies, support the alignment
30 of subnational action with national and global targets, and contribute to upcoming assessments such
31 as the IPCC Special Report on Cities and Climate Change.

34 105 35 36 2. Methods

37 38 39 2.1 Global emission scenarios

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41 In ScenarioMIP-CMIP7, seven IAM systems – AIM 3.0 (Hasegawa *et al* 2017, Fujimori *et al* 2024),
42 COFFEE 1.6 (Zanon-Zotin *et al* 2025), GCAM 8s (Calvin *et al* 2019), IMAGE 3.4 (Stehfest *et al* 2014) ,
43 110 MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM-GAINS 2.1-M-R12 (Fricko *et al* 2017, Krey *et al* 2020, Kishimoto *et al* 2025),
44 REMIND-MAGPIE 3.5-4.11 (Baumstark *et al* 2021, Dietrich *et al* 2019), and WITCH 6.0 (Emmerling *et al*
45 2016) – are used to derive a wide range of plausible emissions futures under different climate
46 policy ambition levels and alternative assumptions on socio-economic development, energy use, and
47 land use. The socio-economic development is prescribed based on the narratives and quantitative
48 drivers of the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) (O’Neill *et al* 2014).
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51 Van Vuuren *et al.* (2025) describe the scenario narratives for the seven illustrative emission and land
52 use futures, ranging from a *High emission* scenario exploring the upper end of plausible future
53 emissions, to a *Very Low emission* scenario limiting the overshoot of 1.5°C and returning to below
54 1.5°C by the end of the century. In view of current country-level backlashes against climate policies
55 and increasing interest in scenarios that study temperature overshoot (Tavoni *et al* 2026), the
56 120 scenario set includes several pathways featuring delayed climate action.

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The *High emission* scenario is characterized by a global rollback and eventual collapse of climate policies, the breakdown of international cooperation, and nations increasingly prioritizing economic and security interests over mitigation efforts. In this fragmented governance landscape, fossil fuel industries remain dominant as public support for climate policies declines, resistance to the energy transition intensifies, and the deployment of low-carbon technologies slows. The *High-to-Low emission* scenario follows a similar emissions pathway over the first half of the century, albeit driven by a different narrative based on high growth and rapid technological change. After 2060 it assumes a sudden surge in climate policy ambition aimed at drastically cutting emissions and upscaling carbon dioxide removal. The *Medium emission* scenario assumes the continuation of existing policies and techno-economic trends. Domestic policy targets such as NDCs and net-zero pledges are not included in this scenario unless a corresponding legislation is in place. The *Medium-to-Low emission* scenario initially assumes current domestic policies and trends as in the M scenario, but moderately increases climate policy ambition after 2040. Although the emissions in this scenario reach net-zero CO₂ globally around the end of the century, it is insufficient to meet the temperature goals of the Paris Agreement. The *Low emission* scenario is consistent with holding warming likely below 2°C. In the near-term, it reflects the NDCs for 2030 and in the long-term it achieves global GHG neutrality. The *Low-to-Negative emission* scenario assumes a continuation of current policies and trends until 2035, delaying substantial emission reductions by another decade. Strong climate policies thereafter trigger deep emission reductions to rapidly achieve net-zero GHG emissions, relying on large-scale carbon dioxide removal (CDR) technologies in the second half of the century to limit the duration of the overshoot of 1.5°C. The *Very Low emission* scenario combines the most ambitious and rapid emission reductions with broad sustainability transformations across all sectors. Its goal is to achieve the lowest plausible peak warming through rapid decarbonization of the electricity supply, deep electrification of energy demand sectors, and behavioral shifts in transportation, consumption, and diets. Sustainable land-use futures further enable the achievement of net-zero GHG emissions without reliance on large-scale CDR options.

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For each of the seven scenario narratives, one scenario quantification by a specific IAM model was selected as a marker scenario (Table 1). In this study, we focus on the seven selected marker scenarios for analyzing urban emission futures.

Table 1: Overview of ScenarioMIP-CMIP7 markers considered. For brevity, the scenarios are referred to as *High, High-Low, Medium, Med-Low, Low, Low-Neg, Very Low* in the paper figures.

Marker Scenario model	Narrative	Global emissions, forcing and warming outcomes
<i>High</i> GCAM 8s	Global rollback and collapse of climate policies, breakdown of international cooperation, nations prioritize security interests. Fossil fuels remain dominant. Based on SSP3,	GHG emissions steadily increase and reach 80 Gt CO ₂ -eq in 2100. Median surface temperature is projected to reach ~3.4°C at the end of the century.
<i>High-to-Low</i> WITCH 6.0	Global rollback of climate policies with rapid economic growth and technological change. Fossil fuels remain dominant. Climate policy surges after 2060, aimed at drastically cutting emissions and upscaling carbon dioxide removal. Based on SSP5.	GHG emissions steadily increase until 2065, closely following the H scenario, and thereafter rapidly decrease to reach net-zero CO ₂ in 2100. Median surface temperature is projected to peak at ~2.9°C between 2080 and 2090.
<i>Medium</i> IMAGE 3.4	Continuation of existing, legislatively backed policies and current techno-economic trends. Targets not yet underpinned by legislation (e.g., NDCs, net-zero pledges) are excluded. Based on SSP2.	GHG emissions decrease by 10% from 2023 to 2050 before stabilizing, thereby remaining above 50 Gt CO ₂ -eq throughout the century. Median surface temperature is projected to reach ~3.0°C at the end of the century.
Medium-to-Low COFFEE 1.6	Current policies and trends as in M until 2040, with moderate increase in climate policy ambition thereafter. Based on SSP2.	GHG emissions are comparable to the M scenario until 2050, and gradually decrease thereafter to reach net-zero CO ₂ by 2100. Median surface temperature is projected to peak at ~2.5°C shortly before 2100.
<i>Low emission</i> MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM-GAINS 2.1-M-R12	Consistent with holding warming likely below 2°C. Reflects NDCs for 2030 in the near-term and achieves greenhouse gas neutrality in the long-term. Based on SSP2.	GHG emissions decrease strongly to reach net-zero CO ₂ by 2070, followed by a gradual decline to reach greenhouse gas neutrality by 2100. Median surface temperature is projected to peak at ~1.8°C in 2060, declining towards ~1.6°C in 2100.
<i>Low-to-Negative emissions</i> AIM 3.0	Current policies and trends until 2035. Strong climate policy thereafter drives deep emission reductions and large-scale carbon dioxide removal. Based on SSP2.	GHG emissions are comparable to the M scenario until 2035, followed by a steep decline to reach net-zero CO ₂ in 2065 and continued net-negative GHG emissions of around -15 Gt CO ₂ -eq from 2090. Median surface temperature is projected to peak at 1.8°C in 2060 and return below 1.5°C in 2100.
<i>Very Low emission</i> REMIND 3.5 - MAgPIE 4.11	Most ambitious and rapid emission reductions to achieve “as low as plausible” peak warming, combined with broad sustainability transformations. Fast power sector decarbonization, deep electrification, behavioral shifts, and sustainable land-use futures. Based on SSP1.	GHG emissions decline rapidly and deeply to reach net-zero CO ₂ by 2050 and greenhouse gas neutrality by 2070. Median surface temperature estimates peak below 1.7°C in 2050 then decline towards 1.4°C in 2100.

* Indicative warming and radiative forcing based on the 50th percentile of MAGICC climate assessment as used in IPCC WG3 AR6 (Guivarch *et al* 2022, Kikstra *et al* 2022). They may deviate from CMIP7, for which scenarios will be re-analyzed with updated historic emission estimates and MAGICC parameterization.

2.2 Downscaling of emission scenarios to urban scale

The method for estimating the urban contribution to future global GHG emissions is comprised of multiple steps (described in detail in Suppl. Mat. S1): (i) downscaling from native IAM regions to country level and harmonization with historical emissions inventories based on a well-established method (Gidden *et al* 2018); (ii) downscaling from country level to grid level with $0.1^{\circ} \times 0.1^{\circ}$ resolution accounting for dynamic changes in subnational evolution of GDP and population; (iii) calculation of urban emissions on national and regional levels based on gridded projection of urban population; and (iv) calculation of urban emissions by city type based on the typology introduced by Montfort *et al.* (2026). These steps are calculated for each sector and emission species individually.

Step (ii) is the most crucial element of this methodology. It downscales projected aggregate country-level emissions for each sector according to the base year spatial pattern of sector emissions (Hoesly *et al* 2025) adjusted for projected changes in the spatial pattern of socio-economic drivers (population (Bondarenko *et al* 2025a, 2025b) or GDP (Paprotny 2025)).

In step (iii), in line with the degree of urbanization (DEGRUBA) approach (Dijkstra *et al* 2021) we allocate emissions from each grid cell to (1) cities, (2) towns and suburbs (peri-urban zones), and (3) rural areas proportional to the population share of each category. Throughout this manuscript, we refer to urban emissions as the aggregate of emissions from cities and towns and suburbs. We focus our analysis on the energy supply, industry, transport, buildings and waste sectors, since human settlements are dominant contributors. We focus the analysis on gross fossil GHG emissions excluding carbon dioxide removal (CDR). Wherever reported, CDR refers to economy-wide deployment (incl. non-urban), since no downscaling was possible to distinguish urban from non-urban CDR.

The grid-based approach here is distinct from other approaches calculating urban emissions within administrative boundaries (Yu *et al* under review), although the global urban share in territorial emissions are roughly comparable (Yu *et al* under review). Importantly, the territorial emissions analyzed here do not account for emissions related to goods and services consumed in cities but produced outside of cities. This approach is in contrast to consumption-based emissions accounting that uses input-output methods downscaled to urban areas (Moran *et al* 2018, Gurney *et al* 2022).

3. Results

3.1 Wide range of urban GHG emission futures

Urban emissions futures span a wide range across scenarios (Figure 1). In the *Medium* scenario, consistent with a continuation of current policies, aggregate urban GHG emissions from the energy supply, industry, transport, buildings and waste sectors are projected to decline from 28 GtCO₂e in 2025 to 25 GtCO₂e in 2050, stabilizing thereafter. In the *High* and *High-to-Low* scenarios, assuming a rollback of climate policies, urban emissions increase to 31-36 GtCO₂e by 2050. *Very Low*, characterized by high climate policy ambition and sustainability-oriented development, implies a reduction of gross GHG emissions from urban areas to 3.7 GtCO₂e in 2050, corresponding to a reduction of 21 GtCO₂e compared to *Medium*.

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3 The development of urban emissions largely reflects the evolution of global GHG emissions in the
4 195 respective scenarios. We find that urban areas account for 66% of global GHG emissions from the
5 considered sectors in 2025, broadly consistent with studies based on historic inventories (Crippa *et al*
6 *2021*, Yu *et al* under review). In *Medium*, the urban share in global emissions increases gradually
7 to 75% by 2100. The urban share in global emissions remains below the urban share in global
8 population. Global average per capita GHG emissions in urban areas in 2025 are 4.5 tCO₂e/cap,
9 200 around 20% lower than the global average, and range between 5.0 tCO₂e/cap in *High-to-Low* and 0.5
10 tCO₂e/cap in *Very Low* in 2050 (Figure 2).

14 3.2 Emission trends and mitigation potentials across sectors

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17 Urban areas account for around 67% of GHG emissions from energy supply and 75% of those from
18 industry in 2025. These sectors also hold the largest potential for emissions reductions. While
19 205 emissions from urban installations only decline slightly in *Medium*, *Very Low* exhibits a 92%
20 reduction in urban energy supply emissions, and an 82% reduction in urban industry emissions by
21 2050 relative to 2025. Residual GHG emissions in deep mitigation scenarios are typically dominated
22 by residual fossil fuel use for bulk material production, such as chemicals, steel and cement (Luderer
23 *et al* 2022, Zanon-Zotin *et al* 2025).

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27 210 Urban areas also dominate emissions from the buildings sector, accounting for more than 60% of its
28 direct emissions, which stem mostly from space and water heating as well as cooking. Importantly,
29 the buildings sector also has substantial indirect emissions from the electricity (e.g., for air
30 conditioning or appliances) and district heating and from construction materials (Cabeza *et al* 2022),
31 which under territorial accounting are represented in the energy supply and industry sectors. In
32 215 absolute terms, direct buildings emissions are projected to decrease from around 2.2 GtCO₂e in 2025
33 to around 1.4 GtCO₂e in 2050 in *Medium*, and 0.16 GtCO₂e in *Very Low*, indicating a substantial
34 mitigation potential from energy efficiency improvements and electrification of heating and cooking.

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38 Transport demand includes both short-distance trips that are predominantly urban and linked to
39 population density, and long-distance travel and freight that is also strongly correlated to economic
40 220 activity (Creutzig *et al* 2022b, Schäfer *et al* 2009). Energy use and emissions from transport are
41 therefore more spatially distributed, and urban areas only account for around half of the territorial
42 emissions of this sector (excluding bunkers, i.e. international aviation and shipping). Under a
43 continuation of current climate policy ambition (*Medium*), urban transport emissions are projected
44 to decrease gradually, as the increasing electrification of road transport offsets the increasing
45 demand, in particular in developing and emerging economies. Even in the *High* and *High-to-Low*
46 225 scenarios with weak climate policies, urban GHG emissions from transport stabilize. By contrast,
47 *Very Low* shows a near-complete elimination of GHG emissions from transport by 2070,
48 corresponding to emission reductions of 2.0 GtCO₂e/yr compared to *Medium*.

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53 The treatment of municipal solid waste and wastewater generates GHG emissions – predominantly
54 230 methane and nitrous oxide –, and almost 80% of these emissions occur within urban areas. Urban
55 waste emissions amount to around 1.5 GtCO₂e in 2025, corresponding to around 5% of total urban
56 GHG emissions. Mitigation options include waste reduction and improved waste treatment (Oo *et al*
57 2024). In *Very Low*, GHG emissions from waste remain around 1.0 GtCO₂e through 2070, making this
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235 sector a relevant contributor to long-term residual GHG emissions under high climate policy
ambition.

Even under the high policy ambition in *Very Low* residual gross GHG emissions from the considered sectors remain at 2.7 GtCO₂e (incl. non-urban) and 2.1 GtCO₂e (urban areas) in 2070. CDR technologies thus play an important role for achieving net-zero emissions.

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Figure 1: (a) Projections of future urban GHG emissions (excluding bunkers, AFOLU and CDR) under the ScenarioMIP marker scenarios. For comparison, dashed lines show total GHG emissions from these sectors including non-urban geographies. (b) Urban share in gross GHG emissions by sector and cross-sectoral (Medium). (c) Sectoral breakdown of GHG emissions for *Medium*, *Very Low*, and reductions in *Very Low* compared to *Medium*.

Figure 2: Urban (positive bars) and economy-wide (dots) per-capita GHG emissions by sector under alternative emission scenarios. Negative CDR component shows per-capita average (incl. non-urban areas) to indicate potential for compensating emissions.

3.3 Urban emissions across different world regions

In terms of world regions, urban GHG emissions are dominated by East Asia, including China, South Asia, including India, and other Asian countries, which combine for 69% of the global total in 2025 (Fig 3a). This dominance reflects the high share of these countries in global population, high share of population dwelling in urbanized areas, and above world-average per-capita GHG emissions in China. African urbanized areas account for only 1.5 GtCO₂e in 2025 due to relatively low urbanization, and per-capita GHG emissions well below global average. Due to growing population, increasing urbanization, and increasing per-capita emissions, Africa's urban GHG emissions are projected to treble until 2070 under *Medium*, making up 18% of the global total emissions at that point, and 23% under the *Very Low* scenario. OECD countries of Europe, North America and the Pacific combine for one fifth of global urban emissions in 2025. Their urban emissions are projected to decline both in absolute and relative terms in *Medium*.

Per-capita urban GHG emission in 2025 vary widely across different world regions, ranging from 1.3 tCO₂e/cap in Africa, to around 2.1-3.6 tCO₂e/cap in South Asia, Latin America, and other Asia, 5 tCO₂e/cap in Europe, 7.5 tCO₂e/cap in North America and Pacific OECD, 8.5 tCO₂e/cap in East Asia, 7.8-9.3 tCO₂e/cap in the fossil-intensive countries of the Middle East and non-EU reforming economies of the former Soviet Union (Figure 3b). Under a continuation of current policy ambition (*Medium*), per-capita emissions decrease moderately in high-income countries, China and, to a weaker extent, fossil-intensive countries, while a slight increase in per-capita emissions is projected for Africa, Latin America and India. Despite some convergence, regional disparities in per-capita

emissions largely persist in *Medium*. In *Very Low*, by contrast, GHG emissions decrease in all world regions, with a convergence of per-capita gross GHG emissions to 0.3-1.2 tCO₂e by 2050. Mitigation potentials thus scale largely with the regional emission patterns projected under weak climate policies. With a difference of 13 GtCO₂e between urban GHG emissions of *Medium* and *Very Low* in 2050, Asia account for more than half of the urban GHG emission reduction potential, particularly in the industry sector. Under *Very Low*, urban GHG emissions in 2050 are below 1 GtCO₂e in Africa and Latin America, while industrialised countries in North America, Europe and the Pacific Region reach net zero by combining deep reductions in gross GHG emission with early upscaling of CDR.

Figure 3: (a) Urban contribution to gross GHG emissions by region in Medium and Very Low. For comparison, total fossil CO₂ emissions from all geographies are shown. (b) Per-capita urban greenhouse gas emissions by sector in different world regions for Medium and Very Low scenarios.

3.4 Urban emissions vary widely across city types

To interpret variation in urban GHG emissions across diverse urban systems, we draw on the global city typology developed by Montfort et al. (2026). The intention of the typology is to group cities with shared characteristics relevant to climate action thus allowing for comparing cities that face similar climate-related challenges. The typology captures the spectrum of urban development (population and population growth, share of population above 65, population density and its change), socioeconomic development (GDP and GDP growth, index of critical infrastructures), and biophysical energy-demand conditions (such as climatic conditions requiring heating or cooling). Leaning on existing IPCC nomenclature (Lwasa et al, 2022), we refer to the four types as emerging, rapidly growing, established, and large and megacities. Emerging cities correspond to smaller, lower-income cities with limited infrastructure, low human development, and high cooling needs; rapidly growing cities represent economically growing cities with intermediate infrastructure, low population density, and rapid horizontal expansion; established cities encompass wealthier cities with strong infrastructure and limited population and economic growth; and large and megacities refer to high-density, fast-growing cities with large population and relatively advanced infrastructure but acute cross-sectoral pressures. Especially in rapidly growing and mega-cities, urban planning is an important lever for climate change mitigation, having a potential to reduce GHG emissions in the construction sector, in building energy use, and in urban transport. Together, these four types cover 69% of urban population, 75% of urban GDP, and 70% of urban GHG emissions in 2025.

Within these typologies, established and rapidly growing cities dominate urban GHG emissions in 2025, together accounting for 13.7 GtCO₂e (Figure 4a). Under *Medium*, emissions from established and rapidly growing cities decline only gradually, whereas emissions from emerging cities increase over time and eventually exceed those of rapidly growing cities. Hence, without deep mitigation, an increasing share of future urban emissions will come from city types that currently have lower per-capita emissions. Under *Very Low*, by contrast, emissions decline rapidly across all city types, with the largest absolute reductions occurring in established and rapidly growing cities.

Per-capita GHG emissions also differ across city types. In 2025, rapidly growing (6.3 tCO₂e/cap) and established cities (6.3 tCO₂e/cap) show the highest per-capita emissions compared with around 2–2.8 tCO₂e/cap in emerging cities and megacities (Figure 4b). The sectoral composition is broadly similar across city types, although rapidly growing cities have relatively larger contributions from energy supply and industry (Figure 4c). Under *Medium*, per-capita emissions decrease slightly in established, rapidly growing and megacities, but rise modestly in emerging cities. Under *Very Low*, by contrast, per-capita emissions decline strongly in all city types and converge to below 1 tCO₂e/cap by 2050.

Figure 4: (a) Urban contribution to gross GHG emissions by city type in *Very Low* and *Medium*. The typology chosen covers around 70% of urban GHG in 2025 (solid line). (b, c) Per capita GHG emissions by sector in different city types.

330 4. Discussion and conclusion

335 Building on a novel and sector-detailed downscaling of ScenarioMIP-CMIP7 pathways, our analysis shows that urban areas account for a dominant and increasing fraction of GHG emissions globally, and hold large potential for emission reductions. Under high climate policy ambition, urban areas can combine for a total of 21 GtCO₂e of GHG emission reductions by 2050 compared to a continuation of current policies and trends, most importantly from transitioning away from fossil fuels for electricity and heat supply, defossilization of industry, and mitigation action in the transportation, buildings and waste sectors. This dominance of energy supply and industry indicates that urban mitigation cannot be understood solely through local demand-side interventions in the transport and buildings sectors, but also depends fundamentally on national and even global infrastructure transitions. Nonetheless, the demand-side interventions (Creutzig et al., 2022), and especially urban planning (Creutzig et al., submitted), remain important and are areas where municipalities have high agency.

345 Urban emissions and emission reduction potentials, both in absolute and in per-capita terms, exhibit pronounced heterogeneity across regions and city types. Asia dominates both current emissions and future mitigation potentials, accounting for around 60% of urban emissions and more than half of the reduction potential. In terms of city types, rapidly growing and established cities hold the largest share in global mitigation potentials. Per-capita emissions levels and mitigation potentials are greatest in fossil-intensive countries of the Middle East, former Soviet Union and China. Urban areas and emerging cities in Africa and parts of Asia are characterized by low per-capita emissions levels. 350 Dedicated climate policies can enable green growth and prevent a replication of emission intensive structures currently observed in other world regions.

Mitigation requires action across all sectors, world regions and city types. For illustration, we table key and dominant options for all six sectors, which can facilitate GHG emission reductions (Table 2). Urban planning strategies are particularly relevant for rapidly growing cities and megacities in Asia and Africa. Other strategies, like building retrofit, will be most important for established cities. Fleet electrification was previously seen as a strategy for richer OECD countries, but energy security concerns and the rapidly declining costs of batteries mean that electric vehicles are now especially advancing in Chinese cities, but more recently also in Africa (Gicha *et al* 2024, Noll *et al* 2026).

360 However, even under very high mitigation ambition, residual emissions will remain. CDR technologies are thus a crucial component of net-zero strategies. Since CDR technologies tend to be land-intensive (Smith *et al* 2015) most CDR potential is situated outside of urban areas. Intra-urban options for achieving CDR include urban trees and greening, wood-based construction, biochar in construction materials, estimated at the order of ~1 GtCO₂/yr (Rodriguez Mendez *et al* 2024).

365 **Table 2:** Illustrative key measures for cities to facilitate deep emission reductions in individual sectors. In addition, municipalities may also consider demand-side action in the food sector, e.g., plant-based diets in public canteens, as options that are not modelled in this paper.

Sector	Main solutions
Buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • heat pumps and low-carbon district heating (Van Heerden <i>et al</i> 2025, Rosenow <i>et al</i> 2025) • energy efficient buildings (such as energy efficiency standards, passive housing, retrofits) (Ürge-Vorsatz <i>et al</i> 2020) • compact urban planning (multi-family housing)
Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fleet electrification and charging infrastructure compact urban planning and transit-oriented development (Ewing and Cervero 2017, Nachtigall <i>et al</i> 2025) • cycling and walking infrastructure (Creutzig <i>et al</i> 2022a, Millard-Ball <i>et al</i> 2025, Hinson <i>et al</i> 2026, Kraus and Koch 2021)
Waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • waste prevention (Möslinger <i>et al</i> 2023) • organic waste diversion to avoid methane on landfills (Oo <i>et al</i> 2024) • methane capture on landfills (Oo <i>et al.</i>, 2024)
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • steel recycling (Onesmo <i>et al</i> 2024, Wu <i>et al</i> 2025) • low-carbon cement (e.g., with biochar) and wood-made buildings (Chen <i>et al</i> 2023)
Energy supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • renewables (rooftop & balcony PV in cities) (Galvin 2026, Zhang <i>et al</i> 2025) • dynamic pricing and battery storage
CDR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • urban trees (Rodriguez Mendez <i>et al</i> 2024) • biochar for buildings (Rodriguez Mendez <i>et al</i> 2024) • wood-based construction (Mishra <i>et al</i> 2022) • waste incineration with carbon capture and storage (Struthers <i>et al</i> 2022)

370 Several limitations should be considered when interpreting these findings. The downscaling approach assumes that sectoral emission intensity reductions at the urban level follow national trends, which may not capture differences in transition dynamics between urban and rural areas. The delineation of urban areas based on gridded population and GDP introduces uncertainty regarding the definition of urban areas. Considering administrative boundaries rather than only urban grid cells would result in a higher urban share in emissions. In addition, the focus on territorial emissions excludes emissions embodied in traded goods, such as imported food or electricity, and therefore does not capture the full carbon footprint of urban consumption. Finally, uncertainties inherent to IAM scenarios propagate into the urban emission estimates.

380 In conclusion, cities are central to achieving deep emission reductions. Realizing the urban mitigation potential requires rapid transformation in the energy supply, industry, buildings, transportation and waste sectors. Urban planning is a central lever to achieving mitigation across building and transport sectors (explored in Creutzig *et al*, same issue). At the same time, the uneven distribution of emissions and mitigation potentials across regions and city types highlights the importance of differentiated and forward-looking strategies. Integrating spatially explicit urban insights into global scenario analysis provides a critical bridge between global climate targets and sub-national climate action.

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